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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE LEGAL PROFESSION: CHALLENGES AND RISKS IN THE AREA OF PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION AND LAWYERS' DUTY OF CONFIDENTIALITY¹

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence tools are gradually entering the practical and fairly ordinary life of our entire society. Many tools and applications that use this new technology can be identified almost "at every step," which reinforces the feeling among individuals that without adopting these innovations, it is impossible to remain competitive compared to other individuals or entrepreneurs who do use these tools. In our view, similar attitudes exist within the practice of various legal professions (lawyers, judges, notaries, etc.), and it will depend on future developments whether these expectations are fulfilled. Specifically in the field of law practice, elements of flexibility, speed, and efficiency in providing legal services to clients come to the forefront. This creates pressure to introduce innovations into everyday practice—otherwise, a solicitor may lose competitiveness compared to others. With this in mind, the authors of this paper examined both the technical and legal challenges and risks that can be identified in the use of artificial intelligence tools in the provision of legal services on an on- . In particular, they focused on whether working with selected AI tools ensures adequate protection of personal data under applicable legislation, and whether the use of AI tools leads, or could lead, to a violation of a solicitor's duty of confidentiality.

Key words: Artificial intelligence, legal practice, personal data protection, duty of confidentiality

Introduction

The world has recently been influenced by a new approach to the use of technological progress, which is reflected in the gradual penetration of artificial intelligence (hereinafter "AI") tools into virtually all areas of life. We dare to predict that where

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